

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

101035819

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

**ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA
WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION
FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE**

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
WP5	D5.4	D29	Report of methodologies for sparking impactful innovation	UU

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Report	Public	

Description (short)
This report brings together a mapping of existing initiatives supporting industry-academy collaborations and entrepreneurship in ENLIGHT universities.

Document Version Control		
Version 0.1	Originated by:	UU
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15586058	

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Introduction and context

ENLIGHT is an alliance formed by nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries (Belgium, Estonia, France, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands, Slovakia, Spain & Sweden). ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the Horizon 2020 Science with and For Society (SwafS) work programme for the ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society), which seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance. In the new phase of ENLIGHT (ENLIGHT 2.0, 2023-2027), the University of Bern joined the alliance which strengthens the diversity and impact of the alliance, furthering its mission to develop a university of the future. ENLIGHT introduced some new elements as part of its strategic direction. This includes the launch of bottom-up calls for interdisciplinary thematic networks and starter grants to promote the development of future-proof education.

The new European Research Area (ERA) plans to improve researchers' employability and at the same time boost transfer to economy by enhancing academy-industry partnerships and inter-sectoral mobility schemes involving industry. The ENLIGHT alliance has gathered a strong knowledge community composed of highly competitive entrepreneurial universities, increasingly connected with businesses and society. The Universities that compose this alliance are different and use a variety of methods for sparking impactful innovation.

Impact is at the core of the ENLIGHT mission and one of the alliance's distinctive features. ENLIGHT aims to undertake a “*fundamental transformation of European Higher Education that empowers learners as globally engaged citizens with state-of-the-art knowledge, skills, and innovation potential to tackle major societal transitions and to promote equitable quality of life and sustainability*”. ENLIGHT seeks to promote an impact-based culture both within and beyond its universities. In order to meet this ambition, there is a need for new ideas, new methods or new ways of using the available methods of collaboration with external societal stakeholders. As the results of ENLIGHT's Impact Work Package show, ENLIGHT partner universities are strongly anchored in a local and regional ecosystem, with solid experience of collaboration, engagement and even co-creation with external societal stakeholders. According to the results of the ENLIGHT Impact Literacy Survey, most universities do have expertise to support research co-creation for research impact. This report is an attempt to both create an inventory of the existing methodologies supporting industry-academy collaborations and entrepreneurship, and identify those methods and expertise that ENLIGHT needs in its new phase. By identifying and focusing on some of the needed methods and expertise for reaching ENLIGHT's desired Impact (indicators introduced by WP8) during coming three years, ENLIGHT academics/ researchers can become more equipped, empowered, and committed to design, as well as implement, challenge-based education programmes and research activities.

So far within the alliance, we have put the method of *AIMday (Academy Industry Meeting)* into test by co-arranging two such events, thereby providing the possibility for the ENLIGHT universities to bring their academics and external organisations together for innovative exchange of knowledge and ideas. This test was fruitful and has provided insights into how local challenges, which are important for the local/host societies, can create new collaborations

between researchers and representatives from different countries which could be beneficial both for local actors and global participants in the long term.

Linked to these experiences, and towards sustainability of the ENLIGHT European Innovation Network, we find that sharing information about this kind of method will create a better understanding and improve the research and innovation support services provided to our researchers. ENLIGHT RISE WP5 has therefore conducted an inventory and produced this report of existing methodologies and initiatives supporting industry-academy collaborations and entrepreneurship. These years of collaboration have proved that each institution of this alliance has something to offer to improve the results of our collaboration as an alliance.

This report, together with the experience gained from the previous tasks, will serve as a foundation for the ENLIGHT RISE governance towards the development of a sustainable ENLIGHT European Innovation Network beyond this pilot phase.

Executive Summary

This report is organised into three sections:

Section 1 presents the methodology used to gather the information about the methodologies for sparking impactful innovation used by each university. Section 2 provides an overview of the results, and the final section presents some recommendations.

Methodology

Table of information about different methods

As a starting point, all partners were asked to fill in a table with the information about their different methods for sparking impactful innovation. Information was collected in a shared table accessible for the partners via SharePoint. In search for a common ground and a better understanding of each other's methods we suggested dividing the table into three parts:

- 1- **Industry-Academy collaborations** (focusing on methods for sparking impactful innovation by research, where the target groups are researchers and industry or external actors)
- 2- **Entrepreneurship** (methods for sparking impactful innovation by business where the target groups are our researchers and PhD students)
- 3- **Support for students** (methods for students' engagement in impactful innovation, when it comes to both collaboration and entrepreneurship)

Uppsala University collaborates with the community in a wide variety of ways and uses a process called 5i which provides structure for collaborations. 5i is a model for collaborations between the University and external parties. It is developed by UU in collaboration with two other universities in Sweden - the universities in Linköping and Örebro. The name 5i refers to the five I's: inspire, identify, initiate, implement, and intensify. These five words define the model and create structure and focus for our efforts in effectively supporting the establishment of new collaborations.

In agreement with the work package team responsible for this report, to create a structure for our work regarding the report, the 5i model is used in the first part of the table - **Industry-Academy collaborations.**

Industry/Academy collaborations					
Activity	Inspire	Identify	Initiate	Implement	Intensify
Objectives	<i>Awareness of possibilities in collaboration. Stimulate new ideas.</i>	<i>Interest in each other and in the subject/issue.</i>	<i>Joint proposal or project plan</i>	<i>Collaborative projects and feasibility studies for collaborations are carried out</i>	<i>Collaborative projects with external funding are carried out. An innovative culture and impactful innovation.</i>

Based on these steps, each university filled the table with relevant information. This model made it easier for the partners to compare their methods and identify the methods which can contribute specifically to the aim and work of the alliance.

For the second part of the table, we used a similar structure to gather information regarding entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship						
Activity	Inspire	Identify	Validate	Start up	Build	Exit
Objectives	<i>Awareness of possibilities. Stimulate new ideas.</i>	<i>Explore values and possibilities</i>	<i>Validate business potential</i>	<i>Identifying and segmenting customers, unique value proposition & channels</i>	<i>Knowledge of business development, financing and what is required to build business concepts and an organization</i>	<i>Successful outlicensing or company launched</i>

And the last part of the table shows the information about different methods and programs each university has for supporting our students.

Students & Impactful innovation						
Methods/ tools	Digital career support	Traineeships	Degree projects and essay adverts	workshops	Events	Job adverts

Interview with representatives from the universities

The table highlights current methods, approaches, support and services for supporting industry-academy collaborations. Supplementary interviews with representatives from each university were conducted and created useful insights for a deeper discussion about the methods among the partners.

During these interviews, we have gone through each part of the table together and described our methods for each other. After these interviews each partner identified related information about the different methods and based on the structure of the table and the target groups completed the table with information about the methods, activities, and responsible organisations.

This group met monthly at the regular work package meetings and had the opportunity to further discuss the process and add additional information to the table which was available for the group via Share point during almost six months.

Results

This report has gathered information about the methods used for impactful innovation within the alliance. By categorising these methods in three different tables and considering the aim of ENLIGHT and the desired Impact, we could compare the methods and identify some of the methods as the recommended suitable method(s) for developing support for impact-driven research and collaboration.

AIMday method was used during *ENLIGHT European Dialogues* to amplify challenge-based research and innovation actions. The aim of these events was to exchange, disseminate and eventually replicate solutions for societal challenges across the regions of our alliance and throughout Europe (act local, think global) along keynotes, regional network meetings, student presentations, discussion panels and thematic core-group workshops on each of our flagship areas.

With the experience from the first AIMday which had a broad theme (Sustainable Urban Development), partners agreed on narrowing down the theme to focus on local challenges and priorities to spark impactful innovative collaborations. The theme for the second European Dialogue was 'Digital Innovation in Health and Well-being' hosted at University of Galway as the Galway region is one of Europe's premier MedTech hubs and University of Galway is at the heart of this ecosystem.

In the following pages, the methods are presented in three different tables for each partner.

Industry/Academy collaborations					
Activity/programme	Inspire	Identify	Initiate	Implement	Intensify
Objectives	<i>Awareness of possibilities in collaboration. Stimulate new ideas.</i>	<i>Interest in each other and in the subject/issue.</i>	<i>Joint proposal or project plan</i>	<i>Collaborative projects and feasibility studies for collaborations are carried out</i>	<i>Collaborative projects with external funding are carried out. An innovative culture and impactful innovation.</i>
University of Bordeaux Activities by Division for partnerships and innovation and TTO	Promotion of our offer of services (participation in exhibitions, booklet, Innovation page on university Website)	Matchmaking meetings Hack Athech (innovation marathon in digital sciences to stimulate new innovative projects)	Support for project emergence: ideation and design thinking workshop after matchmaking, internal	Support for project construction (local, national and European): building a program/project roadmap, managing public-funded collaborative projects	Partner Recognition programs UBfriendly (label, communication, VIP events... Events "Trophy of trophies" : honor all the winners of Innovation prizes on the campus, mobilize communities and contribute to the creation of a feeling of belonging to a major university innovation center
	Networking and Innovation events	Digital matchmaking platform (the Hub)	intensification / seed funding programs (Prematuration, Spark Bordeaux)	Comaturation (company/TTO co-financing to develop the research concept or validate the proof of concept)	Communication manager that will prioritize developing communications and events targeting our SE partners
	Economic sectors roadmap (awareness of innovation needs)	LabCom Bordeaux event (joint lab promoting and identifying event)	Innovation week: bring together initiatives from all our local partners to boost innovation	Protocole tremplin : Preliminary agreement committing stakeholders to organize discussions to structure a framework agreement, identify common themes and bring out projects	Premium policy : personal and strengthened support of our premium partners
	Animation of innovation fostering places and thematic communities	Transition Day : annual event to foster innovation and experimentation projects relating to environmental and societal transitions	Shared industry/sector roadmaps	France Relance (grant to help preserve the human R&D capacities of companies)	"End of contract" procedure (TTO) : identification of results to be valued and assess satisfaction
	Business Development: prospecting, participation in exhibitions	Visit to labs with socioeconomic actors	Shared industry/sector roadmaps		Business Development : repurchase actions
	COT territorial orientation council (a scene to discuss with socioeconomic actors)	DeepTech Tour : a tour of university campuses to put the spotlight on Deeptech, strengthen the link between stakeholders, and initiate new entrepreneurial projects			Propose a simplified structure rather than a "mille-feuille" of organizations to collaborate
<p>Major and Transversal transforming programs for innovation: InnovationS project (Acculturate and raise awareness for innovation / Bring a profound cultural change for researchers, students and employees) and PUI (Develop an action plan at regional scale to accelerate innovation), DREAM project (Diversify the university's resources to support the evolution of our missions)</p>					

Industry/Academy collaborations						impact
Activity/programme	Inspire	Identify	Initiate	Implement	Intensify	
Objectives	<i>Awareness of possibilities in collaboration. Stimulate new ideas.</i>	<i>Interest in each other and in the subject/issue.</i>	<i>Joint proposal or project plan</i>	<i>Collaborative projects and feasibility studies for collaborations are carried out</i>	<i>Collaborative projects with external funding are carried out. An innovative culture and impactful innovation.</i>	
Uppsala University Innovation Partnership Office:	Seminars, workshops/networking/matchmaking, e.g. Theme day	Matchmaking in small- or large-scale e.g. AIM Day	Advice, follow-up meetings after matchmaking. Internal seed funding.	Advice on contract writing, how to handle IP rights and on opportunities for external funding.	IP management plan, innovation by collaboration	
University of Galway 3 different units:	Innovation Office: Attendance at industry meetings e.g. trade conferences, IRDG etc. Research institutes: Industry Liaison Officers Engagement Office for strategic partnerships	Innovation Office: AIMdays Research institutes: Industry Liaison Officers	Research institutes: Industry Liaison Officers	Innovation Office: Attendance at industry meetings e.g. trade conferences, IRDG etc.	Innovation Office: Attendance at industry meetings e.g. trade conferences, IRDG etc.	Impact Officer
Ghent University Central TTO office supporting decentralized thematic business development centra	Engagement Office for strategic partnerships	Business developers identify opportunities for collaboration. Specific for EU projects: EU office account managers identify opportunities	Business developers initiate collaboration, supported by EU office (for EU projects) and/or funding experts at the TTO	Collaboration is implemented by researchers, supported by business developers and TTO (contract support, IP support, ...) For bigger corporates in our region (Umicore, J&J, ArcelorMittal, ...) framework agreements are put in place which facilitate future collaborations	Periodic meetings with bigger corporates in our region having a framework agreement	
Comenius University Project Office (University level) promote industry-academic collaborations; Research and Development Offices of practical faculties	Activities of Science Park and individual faculties, sharing best practices in university webpage and magazine	Ad-hoc relationships based on personal connections (faculty level partnerships prevail) or demand for specific skills, technology and competence	Established partnerships that result in new activities, Project Office that provides support for project applications (university and also faculty level)	Dedicated personal at faculties level, implementation support by project office. Implementation phase is carried out by researchers involved.	Initiative to intensify industry-academia collaboration is concentrated at the faculties level	

Industry/Academy collaborations					
Activity/programme	Inspire	Identify	Initiate	Implement	Intensify
Objectives	<i>Awareness of possibilities in collaboration. Stimulate new ideas.</i>	<i>Interest in each other and in the subject/issue.</i>	<i>Joint proposal or project plan</i>	<i>Collaborative projects and feasibility studies for collaborations are carried out</i>	<i>Collaborative projects with external funding are carried out. An innovative culture and impactful innovation.</i>
University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) Innovation and Transfer Office (includes the TTO)	Enterprise clusters (Energy, ICT; Industry) organize on-line technical workshops for their partners and periodically the University presents technical capabilities and actives for exploitation. Attendance to fairs, congresses, etc.	Matchmaking meetings, Specific one-to one meeting with enterprises, etc.	Development of technical proposal for discussion; teleconferences with industry to assess the collaboration possibilities in one specific matter	Dedicated personnel for contract management, patents application, negotiation of licenses Dedicated personnel for agreements Specific call University-enterprise-society with internal funds.	Attendance at industry meetings e.g. trade conferences, IRDG etc. Creation of the University-Enterprise " classroom". A place for rese
Groningen University One (central) team divided in 4 units, funded and organized in different ways.	Different activities such as "Meets and greets", theme events. Attendance at industry meetings and events.	External relations coordinators from central organization and faculty Business developers identify opportunities for collaboration.	Advice, follow-up meetings after matchmaking. Internal seed funding.	Collaboration is implemented by researchers, supported by business developers and TTO (contract support, IP support, ...) For strategic partnerships, framework agreements are put in place which facilitate future collaborations	Periodic meetings with the strategic partners having framework agreements
Göttingen University The Transfer and Startup Hub is a part of the research and transfer department, together with the national, EU and international grants office. Regional collaboration as part of SNIC South Lower Saxony Innovation Campus. Collaboration in Göttingen Campus (most research institutes in Göttingen)	Specialized conferences (Praxis forum). Business contact subgroup	Innovation Scouts in combination with Technology Advisors. Innovation Managers.	Advice and follow up, attendance at industry meetings e.g. Measurement Valley, Wissenschaftsregion-Meetup	Grant application support ZIM, contract support, IP advice and connecting with MBM Science Bridge (IP Management)	IP management plan., Innovation by collaboration
University of Tartu Centre of Entrepreneurship and Innovation	Theme events, meeting of group of technology transfer specialists form institutes	Matchmaking meetings	advice, shared industry interests through CRM	IP handling, advise on contract negotiations	comminucation manager, feedback surveys

Entrepreneurship						
Activity/programme	Inspire	Identify	Validate	Start up	Build	Exit
<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Awareness of possibilities. Stimulate new ideas.</i>	<i>Explore values and possibilities</i>	<i>Validate business potential</i>	<i>Identifying and segmenting customers, unique value proposition & channels</i>	<i>Knowledge of business development, financing and what is required to build business concepts and an organization</i>	<i>Successful outlicensing or company launched</i>
University of Bordeaux Activities by Division for partnerships and innovation (UbeeLab) and TTO	Hackathon Pepita ECA for PhD : PhD students work by teams on companies issues Hackathon INRIA (Hackatech) : master degree students, PhD and other attendees work for 2 days on startup projects Marathon of creation (2 days sensitization for IUT students) UB Create week (entrepreneurship sensitization week for international masters) A dozen of other sensitization actions for 1st year student to PhD each year. Many other events, interventions, testimonials to inform hundreds of students each year. More than 1000 UB students sensitized each year.	Student Life Observatory (list of student entrepreneurs). PEPITE ECA delivers the national student status -> 173 student entrepreneurs supported by UBeE Lab for 2023-2024. National student entrepreneur status	UBeE Lab uses a methodology based on GRP Business Model to support the student entrepreneurs UBooster contest: each year UB students can attendee to our contest. The 5 finalist projects share 15k€ dotations. Link'UB: For 2 days each year more than 60 meetings are organized between UBeE Lab student entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship local ecosystem actors (incubators, technopoles, communities, financials...)	UBeE Lab individual and collective support + orientation in ecosystem (startup specific) Incubation Chrysalink : support disruptive innovation projects that will lead to the creation of future start-ups French Tech LAB scholarship supporting the potential for start-up creation and market access for innovative technological projects UBeE Lab identifies best students startup projects to direct them towards specialized incubators or Technopoles to increase their success chances Use of Innovation law which allows the researchers to : become manager/partner of a start-up, bring scientific support, participate in capital and/or in managing boards of an existing company promoting/exploiting research results	Building economic sector roadmap UBeE Lab proposes more than 50 collective workshops per year, animated by its experts' network, to increase specific entrepreneurship knowledges of the student's entrepreneurs UBeE Lab collective support and network	Meeting with regional incubators Ecosystem speed meeting Link'UB event Hackafond
	University of Tartu Program Science to Business (SB)	Seminars workshops	coaching, consultations	IP analyses, business validation	Business development support by Spin-off Team, teambuilding, coaching	Sales techniques, business development coaching,

Entrepreneurship							Licencing Outlicensing	Impact
Activity/programme	Inspire	Identify	Validate	Start up	Build	Exit		
<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Awareness of possibilities. Stimulate new ideas.</i>	<i>Explore values and possibilities</i>	<i>Validate business potential</i>	<i>Identifying and segmenting customers, unique value proposition & channels</i>	<i>Knowledge of business development, financing and what is required to build business concepts and an organization</i>	<i>Successful outlicensing or company launched</i>		
Uppsala University Supporting activities by UU Innovation	Seminars, workshops	NABC, lean canvas etc	Market analyses, IP analyses	Build teams, pitch training, revenue model, investments.	Business law, competence and board, IP strategy, investment and financing for growth, sales technique and branding	Investor meetings, partnering with existing companies		
University of Galway	Innovation Office: Tier 1 training = IMPACT SERIES Innovation Office: Ad hoc training for individual units	Innovation Office: Tier 2 training = IMPACT ACCELERATOR	Innovation Office: Tier 2 training = IMPACT ACCELERATOR	Innovation Office: Tier 2 training = IMPACT ACCELERATOR Innovation Office: patent filing and prosecution	Innovation Office: Tier 3 training = IMPACT START Innovation office: licensing, shareholders agreement etc.	Innovation Office: Tier 3 training = IMPACT START Innovation office: licensing, shareholders agreement etc.	Innovation office: sales and negotiation with licensee. In-Part website	Impact Officer
Ghent University For students and researchers willing to start a company NOT based on their research: DO! the Ugent Centre for Entrepreneurship For researchers looking to start a company based on their research (spin-off): Venture Track at the TTO	DO! has a number of inspiration programs. e.g. Research to Market, Start for Future DO! and TTO organize together the Spin-off café	DO! : Expedition DO! program: 7 months program for students/researchers to identify business opportunity	DO! : business validation during second phase of Expedition DO! DO! : coaching sessions for students and researchers + co-working space TTO: validation of business potential during Venture Track, together with business developers			Meeting with venture capital fund and researchers, facilitated by TTO Ghent University Incubation Centre (IIC) to provide office and lab space License agreement between spin-off and TTO to conclude Venture Track		

Entrepreneurship						
Activity/programme	Inspire	Identify	Validate	Start up	Build	Exit
<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Awareness of possibilities. Stimulate new ideas.</i>	<i>Explore values and possibilities</i>	<i>Validate business potential</i>	<i>Identifying and segmenting customers, unique value proposition & channels</i>	<i>Knowledge of business development, what is required to build business concepts</i>	<i>Successful outlicensing or company launched</i>
Comenius University Study programs on Bachelor and Master level; Individual courses in the field of Entrepreneurship are offered across the whole University; Entrepreneurial club (faculty level); Scientific Park incubator (not working at the moment)	Dedicated events such as FallingWallsLab at the University level, Collaboration with established companies as well as startups on pedagogical process at Faculty of Management	Through pedagogical process and Entrepreneurial Club at the Faculty of Management; Connections with partners such as coworkings and nation entrepreneurial support agency.	Scientific Park incubator (not working at the moment) and entrepreneurial club at the Faculty of Management; Connections with partners such as coworkings and nation entrepreneurial support agency.	Close cooperation with external coworkings (which run incubation and acceleration programs) and nation entrepreneurial support agency	Close cooperation with external coworkings (which run incubation and acceleration programs) and nation entrepreneurial support agency; available options for funding	None
University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) Three entrepreneurship programs (one in each province) co-funded by the province administrations. BIZKAIA--> Zitek https://zitek.eus/en/inicio-en/ GIPUZKOA--> Entrenari <a "="" href="https://entrenari.com/en/ARABA--> Inizia https://inizia.eus/	Workshops for entrepreneurship promotion among the researchers of the University. Awareness of the University services and facilities for students and researchers. Entrepreneurship master	Prizes for entrepreneurship projects. The prizes include a financial contribution and mentoring programs - Youth Entrepreneurship Scholarship. - Best doctoral thesis with the opportunity to be a business project - Prize to best new i& innovative initiatives - Patent applications	The identified projects in the previous phase have access to a free training and mentoring program to define the project	Once the spin-off is going to be implemented there are public funds to support the beginning- the University advise in the achievement of the public funds	Once the spin-off is implemented the University helps finding investment, inviting the spin-off to events, and advertising it through its contacts.	The University does not take part in any of the spin-offs., so there isn't an exit phase.
University of Groningen 4 units, partly conventional TTO activities. Funded and organized in different ways, but collaborating closely in one (central) domain (knowledge utilization & entrepreneurship)	Awareness raising on scientific entrepreneurship, support in finding the right next steps Extra-curricular Entrepreneurship trainings	Advice and information on intellectual property (IP team) Workshops, coaching and relevant network development (Venture Lab)	Patent application and support in the process (IP team) Helping you develop from idea to business plan through Workshops, coaching and relevant network development (Venture Lab)	Business development support (SBGG) Workshops, coaching and relevant network development (Venture Lab)	Business Development coaching (SBGG) Workshops, coaching and relevant network development (Venture Lab) Seed investment (RUG Ventures)	Support in licensing your IP to your own startup or to an established company (SBGG) Collaboration with the ecosystem to increase success of Strat up and move to scale up
Göttingen University Transfer and Startup Hub, Professor of Entrepreneurship Education.	Seminars, workshops Lift-Off Startup Competition, social media LinkedIn and Instagram	Startup consultations, Lift-Off, YES Workshops Young Entrepreneurs in Science	Expert consultations, Market analyses, IP analyses. Pre-incubator, Life Science Incubator, Incubator and Accelerators	Pre-incubator, Life Science Incubator LSF, Incubator and Accelerators	Coworking spaces, support in business model development, pitch training	Partnering with existing companies, financing workshops
						Licensing MBM Science bridge

Students & Impactful innovation						
Methods/tools	Digital career support	Traineeships	Degree projects and essay adverts	workshops	Events	Job adverts
Uppsala University CareerGate, a portal targeted at all of the University's students and alumni	A system used by almost 600 European higher education institutions to highlight a larger international range of job adverts and events to those students seeking an international career path	UU CareerGate	UU CareerGate	UU CareerGate	UU CareerGate	UU CareerGate
University of Bordeaux Activities by Division for partnerships and innovation (UbeeLab), and TTO and Division for education and innovation	New hybrid module on entrepreneurship Innovation training/modules catalog	Career and internship office LACT: transversal skills laboratory Develop the transversal skills of students and staff including innovate in a world in transition to find innovative solutions to societal and environmental transition challenges. PEPITE: Student Center for Innovation, Transfer and Entrepreneurship	Disrupt Campus: innovation and digital transformation training program Ocean i3: New learning by doing modules PEPITE: Student Center for Innovation, Transfer and Entrepreneurship - Student-Entrepreneur Diploma	Hackaton Marathon of creation	Innovation week: bring together initiatives to boost innovation	Career and internship Office
University of Galway		Academic units e.g. Business school	Academic units e.g. Business school	Academic units e.g. Business school	Ideas Lab	Careers Office
Göttingen University SNIC Certificate, EE Entrepreneurship Education, Startup Kit (online learning platform EE)			Praxisarbeit SNIC, Stellenwerk online portal. CIDAS Campus Institute for Data Science Meetup with students and companies	Praxisseminar SNIC (challenges from companies)-workshops, Impact measurement, business model canvas, how to present and negotiate, job interview preparation etc. Hackathon	Praxisbörse, an in person career forum, SNIC site visits at companies, recruiting dinner	Stellenwerk online Job portal

Students & Impactful innovation						
Methods/tools	Digital career support	Traineeships	Degree projects and essay adverts	workshops	Events	Job adverts
Ghent University						
<p>DO!: center for entrepreneurship organizes the Dare to Venture master courses accessible for all MSc students at the university</p> <p>DO! and Green Office Ugent organize calls for challenges for societal stakeholders, which can lead to bachelor or master theses, group assignment, ...</p> <p>UGent career hub offers support for all MSc and PhD students</p>		<p>Companies can offer opportunities to the UGent career hub</p>	<p>DO! and Green Office call for challenges for societal stakeholders can lead to degree projects</p> <p>Companies can offer opportunities to the UGent career hub</p>	<p>Expedition DO! has a track for entrepreneurial students</p>	<p>UGent career hub</p> <p>UGent graduation fair</p>	<p>UGent career hub</p>
Comenius University						
<p>Entrepreneurial and Innovation courses available across the university offered by Faculty of Management</p>		<p>Obligatory internship for bachelor and master students at Faculty of Management; Erasmus + internships offered to students to work abroad</p>		<p>related to dissemination activities of particularly Erasmus+ projects or others</p>	<p>FallingWallsLab</p>	<p>Available job offers information provided by study coordinators to students</p>
University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU)						
<p>Entrepreneurial and innovation activities available also for students</p>		<p>University-enterprise-society "classrooms" for training and research activities. More than 45 classroom with big and medium enterprises</p>	<p>University-enterprise-society "classrooms" for training and research activities. More than 45 classroom with big and medium enterprises</p>	<p>Entrepreneurship Conferences for students</p>	<p>Employment forum once a year. It is for free for enterprises but to participate they have to offer at least two jobs.</p>	<p>University has its own job advert and employment service for graduates</p>
University of Groningen						
<p>Entrepreneurial and Innovation courses offered within most faculties</p>		<p>VentureLab North</p>	<p>Hybrid research group sustainable polymers GDBC</p>	<p>VentureLab North GDBC</p>	<p>VentureLab North GDBC</p>	<p>UG Career Services</p>
University of Tartu						
<p>Entrepreneurial and Innovation courses offered by Scholl of Economics and Business Administration</p>		<p>StartUp lab activities, Futulab activities</p>	<p>Academic units</p>		<p>Marketing Club, sTARTUp Day</p>	

Recommendations

These sources of experience and methods can serve as a foundation for the ENLIGHT RISE governance towards the development of a sustainable ENLIGHT European Innovation Network beyond this pilot phase. With the condition that the related and involved staff get the possibility to identify some of these methods and analyse this information together to identify the areas of improvement for each university.

ENLIGHT aims to undertake a “fundamental transformation of European Higher Education that empowers learners as globally engaged citizens with state-of-the-art knowledge, skills, and innovation potential to tackle major societal transitions and to promote equitable quality of life and sustainability”. ENLIGHT seeks to promote an impact-based culture both within and beyond its universities, including the promotion of a model of good practice of impact-directed management and the integration of impact across higher education, research and innovation.

The alliance created the possibility for the partners to share the information about the methods for supporting their academics and students for impactful innovations but creating the opportunity for practicing some of these methods together, was very limited. Even if experience as such was limited to arranging just two AIMday-events during ENLIGHT European Dialogues and some of the ENLIGHT Regional Academies, it created deeper understanding of the needs.

The collection of information for this report together with the interviews and discussions related to our joint experience of collaboration in the alliance of ENLIGHT highlighted the importance of testing some of the methods in international context and sharing practical experience as we test and/or develop some methods.

According to the impact assessment conducted by RISE WP6, from a societal perspective, this type of collaborations among the partners have not only led to the identification of local/regional challenges, also have contributed to identifying and proposing innovative solutions to tackle these and other identified challenges. And the results of the ENLIGHT Impact Survey show that:

- the majority of ENLIGHT learners, academics, support staff and societal stakeholders recognise feeling being part of the solving process of real challenges.
- it facilitated the interconnection between local/regional quadruple-helix collaborations at European level.
- it has led to the exchange and transfer of regional ecosystems' experiences and/or solutions to other contexts.”¹

¹ RISE WP6 D6.8 D115 the Narrative of Change, https://impact.enlight-eu.org/system/files/2024-03/231026_D115_Pilot%20Cases%20Narratives%20with%20numbers_FINAL.pdf

The diagram below (figure 1) illustrates the ENLIGHT Regional Academies' expected outcomes and desired impact, as well as how these desired changes are expected to happen, taking into consideration its inputs (resources for its implementation), the specific activities carried out by the team (both in the context of WP5 Outreach and WP2 ENLIGHT Challenge Based Learning), and their outputs (the products deriving directly the activities).

Figure 1 Theory of Change 5.0 of the ENLIGHT Regional Academies action line

Considering the desired Impact and related activities and our source of valuable methodologies, the main question is what we can improve together?

To keep up the good work of facilitating the interconnection between the local/regional quadruple-helix collaborations at European level for impactful innovation, we need to gain more shared practical experience by testing and developing some of our methods together.

By arranging a staff week with focus on the methods and consideration of our international perspective, we can become better equipped with methods and tools to support our academics to connect and engage with external stakeholders and fully grasp and assess the impact generated by HE institutions.

Both mapping reports conducted by RISE WP5 (report of the gaps & opportunities and this report on the methodologies for sparking impactful innovation), together with the experience gained from organizing AIMdays can be used by ENLIGHT universities to enhance academy-industry partnerships.

As recommended by the report of the gaps and opportunities², for instance, by developing platforms or databases to facilitate matchmaking and knowledge sharing among researchers, entrepreneurs, and organizations, the ENLIGHT RISE Alliance can position itself as a frontrunner in fostering collaboration, driving innovation, and nurturing talent.

To contribute to the development of a sustainable ENLIGHT European Innovation Network beyond this pilot phase we share knowledge about our best practices by recommending some of partners' initiatives in the following pages. These methods can contribute to both the arrangement of the future Regional Academy events and the support for impact-driven research and collaboration related to the future Thematic Networks in ENLIGHT 2.0.

² [D5.3 ENLIGHT RISE Recommendations on gaps and opportunities in the market for skills and innovation_public.docx](#)

Recommended methods

Ghent University:

- **Research to market**

A six-monthly workshop in which PhD and postdoc researchers are challenged to think about bringing their research to the market. It is a three-day training and coaching session based on a research canvas methodology. The session is concluded with pitch towards a jury who can further advise these people on potential next steps.

- **Call for challenges**

Centre for Entrepreneurship, DO! has a yearly 'call for challenges' in which challenges can be presented by companies, governments, organisations, NGO's ... which can be tackled by students. For each of these challenges a suitable instrument is sought (bachelor thesis, master thesis, project assignment, ...) so that students can work on it. Conditions for the collaboration are agreed between the organisation, the students, and the responsible teacher.

Comenius University:

- **Intrapreneurship**

Faculty of Management offers a dynamic course called "Intrapreneurship" which strongly emphasizes collaboration with practical experience. Throughout this course, students engage in team-based projects that tackle real-world challenges, guided by design thinking and service design principles. This hands-on approach allows students to develop innovative solutions to complex problems. Notably, a continuous feedback loop is established, involving both university instructors and consultants from the industry, ensuring that the solutions devised are not only creative but also highly relevant and applicable in real-world scenarios. Through this holistic learning experience, students not only acquire theoretical knowledge but also gain invaluable practical skills.

- **New Venture Strategy and Financing**

Faculty of Management offers a course called New Venture Strategy and Financing, which focuses on a close partnership with coworking spaces and particularly start-up ventures. Employing the "Disciplined Entrepreneurship" methodology, students delve into authentic challenges faced by start-ups, fostering a deep understanding of entrepreneurial dynamics. Through this experience, students develop strategic insights crucial for launching and sustaining new ventures. The course not only equips students with theoretical knowledge but also instils practical skills, ensuring that the solutions they devise are innovative and also highly actionable for start-up enterprises.

The University of Göttingen

- **Praxis Seminare**

We offer practical workshops called Praxis Seminare, where students work on questions from regional stakeholders (including companies) on specific topics in seminars. The student teams, which may be interdisciplinary, examine issues from different perspectives and then present the results to both the company and the lecturer (e.g. also in combination with an excursion). The contact between companies and seminars is established by the department which maintains the university's business contacts.

- **LIFT-OFF start-up competition**

The competition is aimed at people interested in starting a business as well as active founders from all disciplines. As part of the competition, participants can participate in various events and workshops on entrepreneurship as well as a mentoring program to (further) develop their start-up idea within five months. Finally, the best teams are allowed to pitch their start-up idea to a big audience. In addition to the priceless impulses and experiences there are also attractive cash and non-cash prizes to be won, which are awarded by a jury.

University of the Basque Country

- **clusters events**

The University is very close to the existing enterprise cluster system in the Basque Country. The main cluster are devoted to Energy, ICT, Health and Industry. The clusters organize on-line technical workshops for their partners and periodically the University presents technical capabilities and actives for exploitation. The clusters events are an opportunity that the University takes advantage to make the Industry aware of the research lines and activities.

- **Co-funded entrepreneurship programs**

Three entrepreneurship programs (one in each province) are co-funded by the province administrations. And in the three programs technical staff from the University and technical staff from the province administration collaborate in the entrepreneurship program. The University fosters and looks for opportunities and the province administration assess the entrepreneurs in the existing funding programs, the preparation of the proposal.

- BIZKAIA--> Zitek <https://zitek.eus/en/inicio-en/>
- GIPUZKOA--> Entreprenari <https://entreprenari.com/en/>
- ARABA--> Inizia <https://inizia.eus/>

Some of the activities carried out by the University to foster entrepreneurship:

- Workshops for entrepreneurship promotion among the researchers of the University.
- Awareness of the University services and facilities for students and researchers.
- Entrepreneurship master of the University.
- Prizes for entrepreneurship projects. The prizes include financial contribution and mentoring programs
- Youth Entrepreneurship Scholarship.
- Prize for the Best doctoral thesis with the opportunity to be a business project
- Prize to best new innovative initiatives
- Support on patent applications and licencing negotiations

Once the spin-off is created, the University counts with 6 incubator premises: 4 in the province of Bizkaia, 1 in San Sebastian (Gipuzkoa) and 1 in Vitoria-Gasteiz (Araba), so that the entrepreneurs can select the most suitable location for their new business project.

- **University-enterprise-society classrooms**

The University founded twenty years ago the first two University-enterprise-society "classrooms" for training and research activities. Currently the University has more than 45 classroom with big and medium enterprises, technological centers and research institutions, and social institutions. Each classroom is usually attached to a specific research line and the Director of the Classroom is a University professor attached to a research group specialist in the subject.

This approach between university and other entity allows to collaborate in subjects that are of interest of the enterprises and technological centers, having influence and focusing also the Research activities and project of the research groups. The activities carried out in the classrooms are:

- Master's thesis
- PhD Thesis
- Research project
- Dissemination activities

Bordeaux University

- **The hub**

The hub is a digital matchmaking platform. It is a collaborative platform structured into themes allowing stakeholders in the socio-economic world to have access to all university resources: high-level scientific expertise, cutting-edge technologies or innovations, specific equipment, adapted structures and spaces. <https://thehub-bordeaux.fr/#/>

- **UBee Lab**

Bordeaux University student incubator, offers individual and collective support to student entrepreneurs with the national student entrepreneur status. This status allows all young people with a baccalaureate and above to develop their entrepreneurial project for at least one academic year. 173 student entrepreneurs are supported by UBee Lab for 2023-2024. For example, during the Link'UB event (2 days each year) more than 60 meetings are organized between UBee Lab student entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship local ecosystem actors (incubators, technopoles, communities, financials...)

- **Disrupt Campus**

Bordeaux Innovation and digital transformation training program, Disrupt Campus offers students, from all sectors, the opportunity to discover the challenges of innovation and transitions by working, in project mode, on a concrete case provided by a company, a public establishment, a local authority or an association.

University of Galway

- **Impact Series**

Currently, Europe is trailing behind other regions in effectively translating research and innovation activities into concrete economic benefits. One factor contributing to this situation is the variation in success among different European regions as measured by the European Innovation Scoreboard. Universities are at the heart of innovation and have the potential to be the catalyst for new impactful innovation in the region.

The University of Galway in Ireland has developed a three-tiered impact and entrepreneurial training series (Impact Series) to stimulate the translation of research projects to outcomes with real-world economic and societal impacts. Funded by Horizon Europe, the University of Galway is working in partnership with the University of Turin and Riga Technical University to roll out the Impact Series in a moderate innovator (Italy) and emerging innovator (Latvia), through the INNOV-8-2-CREATE project (innov-8-2-create.eu). The Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (ASTP) are partners providing dissemination and communication leadership for the project.

The overarching objective of the project is to deliver long-term impact through international knowledge exchange and cooperation while also delivering real-world impacts at the local and regional levels.

The INNOV-8-2-CREATE project is widening the participation of multiple actors in the innovation process across Europe. The success of the programme can be attributed to the active participation of diverse innovation stakeholders from across the quadruple helix (i.e., university, industry, state and society). The work completed so far clearly illustrates the innovation potential and in modest and emerging innovation countries. To create a long-lasting impact, over the next year we will produce a repeatable template for this collaborative innovation training and we are now looking to partner with other universities wishing to replicate the successful INNOV-8-2-CREATE model.

- **IdeasLab**

IdeasLab is University of Galway's student innovation hub arranging activities:

Enterprise Challenges: Students work with our industry partners to solve real world problems. Participants receive training in team building, design thinking, business modelling, and storytelling. Each team will also visit and receive mentorship from our industry partners - Aerogen, Medtronic, Boston Scientific, Mbryonics, Galway International Arts Festival, Veryan, SAP, Rent the Runway and Channel Mechanics.

Internship programme: A 10 week, paid internship experience for students in University of Galway. Internships are competitively awarded each semester.

Empathy Lab: A physical lab on the UG campus that has empathy tools and frameworks to support students in developing their empathic skills and create human centric solutions to real world problems.

Coaching and Mentoring: Mentoring forms part of all programmes within IdeasLab, in addition to being a bookable service for students. *Innovation Sandbox:* A testing and prototyping environment where the IdeasLab team work with industry to test and validate projects.

Start100 Summer Accelerator: The Start100 programme is open to teams of students with an early-stage business idea. Support provided to the teams includes space, funding, mentorship, and access to networks of alumni, partners, and investors.

Uppsala University:

- **AIMday**

A method to let representatives from organisations set the agenda by submitting questions that they want to discuss with academics. AIMday has one objective – to match the needs of organisations for new knowledge with academic expertise. The process includes six defined steps from preparatory work to follow-up – about six to eight months: Plan & Prepare, Invite organisations to submit questions, Encourage academics to sign up for questions, Matchmaking and scheduling, Meeting day, Follow-up. AIMday has a well-developed digital platform and has also international hubs. These together with its' clear process and structure makes it a suitable and easy method to apply in different international context. <https://aimday.se/>

- **VFS**

Verification for collaboration (VFS in Swedish) is a funding opportunity to initiate new collaboration projects between researchers at Uppsala University and private, public or non-profit organisations. With a simple setup: a project, nine months, at least two partners of which one is from academia and one is an external actor.

Tartu University:

- **The pre-incubation programme “From Science to Business!”**

The programme is designed for researchers and research teams from the University of Tartu and Tallinn University of Technology who have a product or service, based on intellectual capital and/or infrastructure and keen interest towards entrepreneurship.

Programme objectives:

- Identify the business potential of participants' research.
- Introduce researchers to various opportunities for creating and developing science-based companies.
- Provide support in finding alternative commercialization options (e.g., creating a spin-off company or licensing research results)
- Participants will gain the most important skills and knowledge for founding their science-based company and commercializing their research over a 10-week period.
- Seminars will take place once a week simultaneously in Tartu and in Tallinn.
- Depending on participants, the program will be conducted in Estonian or English. For participants the program is free.
- Seminars are interactive, and after having covered specific topics, participants can also arrange a separate 30-minute consultations with experts.

Groningen University:

- **ExtraCurricular Course on Entrepreneurship**

The ExtraCurricular Course on Entrepreneurship (ECCE) as a first introduction to entrepreneurship is a hands-on course, where students will receive a short introduction to the weekly topic, after which they will work in teams with fellow entrepreneurial students from all faculties to put their new entrepreneurial skills in practice. Every evening ends with a guest speaker, sharing their real-life experiences. Then they can chose either entrepreneurship or they may look for development of their ideas and perhaps even find future team members - there are plenty of opportunities for everyone. Sessions are open for any (PhD) student from the UG and (if places available) others who wish to participate.

- **Inter/Transdisciplinary campuses related to the regional innovation strategy / University of the North**

The campuses and hybrid learning environments in Groningen are unique because they are developed from the idea of continuous learning lines. Vocational training, Universities of applied science and university institutes work together with companies to develop learning and working environments that work on the transitions of our time: energy, health and digitization. As a result, the business community gathered surrounding these themes is never far away and there is sufficient attention to human capital in the region. University of the North, plays a central role in this process.

- **Schools for Science & Society**

Society is faced with major issues that require innovative approaches, across disciplines and institutions. The University of Groningen comprises all branches of science, as well as technology—the motive and means to work with four Schools for Science & Society on four societal issues: energy and climate, digitization and artificial intelligence, sustainable society, and more healthy years. In doing so, it engages in conversation with the public and collaborates with citizen scientists, educational institutions, governments, and the business community.

Conclusion

As mentioned earlier in the recommendation section, these different methods and initiatives provide the ENLIGHT alliance with valuable practical knowledge which can contribute to the development of a sustainable ENLIGHT European Innovation Network beyond this pilot phase. Sharing the knowledge about these best practices will contribute to both the arrangement of the future Regional Academy events and the support for impact-driven research and collaboration related to the future Thematic Networks in ENLIGHT 2.0.

Since the knowledge about these practices includes both general information and relevant expertise around implementing of such methods, sharing these knowledge needs a network of experts. Experts who are well-aware of the available methods and the needs and interests of their own academic organisations.

Domain Expert Network is one of the outputs of RISE which will continue on and contribute to ENLIGHT 2.0 by collaboration with the European Support Network (ESN). ESN is a research support group with 2 key objectives:

1. To support the research outputs of the ENLIGHT thematic networks (ETNs)
2. Supporting broader alliance research collaboration

The ESN will draw on the expertise of the RISE Domain Expert Networks/existing communities of practice to facilitate best practice between ETNs. European Support Network is dependent on RISE Domain Network experts for knowledge sharing events and training to support ETNs research and external collaboration goals. The Domain Export Network have henceforth the possibility to not only share the knowledge, also provide needed support, for instance, for the future thematic networks.

Therefore, this report concludes that the contact persons contributing to this report are needed in the Domain Export Network. This group is recommended to be part of the network with a primarily plan to get together online three times a year. In dialogue with the European Support Network (ESN), they collectively decide the themes for each meeting around Impactful Innovation and ETNs' needs and challenges.